

COMPONENT ANALYSIS IN THE TRANSLATION OF OCCASIONALISMS

Saliyeva Shakhlo Saidaliyevna

Teacher of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Email: shakhlo.rakhimova.84@mail.ru

Phone number: +99891 154 16 14

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8020576>

Annotation: In this article under the concept of the occasionalism, we mean individually and authoritative and potential words that have the following distinctive features: belonging to speech; authorship; dependence on the context; non-export capacity; the availability of an additional stylistic load.

Key words: occasionalism, translation, language, analysis, definition.

Translation of occasionalism, which in his work P. Newmark calls the term New Coinages, is a purely creative process that requires the subdirectory transformer and mortality. The author notes that when capping, you need to pay attention not only to equivalent morphemes, but also for an additional semantic load that they can carry. This phenomenon is considered in the framework of phonostetics. Definition of this science offers Ramond Hickey: "It is a subarea of phonetics concerned with the way to the content of the phonetics concerned and the way the" the "combination of the sounds of FL in words that mean a fast flow or fast movement: flow, fluid, flee, fluent, flux, fling. If the word has an additional phonostetic effect, it should be translated using a premise that produces in the Phase the same effect.

In translation of the P. Newmark advises to pay attention to an alliteration, the onomatopoeia and the association. V.S. Vinogradov also recognizes that an individually copyright word is great interest to translate: "It is diverse and defined not only by the character and the latitude of the use of lexical and grammatical resources of the language, not only of the irregularity of the paths of the author and the manner of his letter, but also the features of the author's neologisms. The author focuses on the fact that in the author's neologism, the value of individual and authorities neologisms is "formed, the form of the individual and regional union" (grapes of the investigation and context). Proceeding from this, VS Vinogradov offers the following two ways to translate the OL: "The dual nature of the value of the occasionalism word allows the translator to kill author's neologisms and create their own Okacaislism, with the requirements of the context". . Among the reasons that cause the interpreter to abandon the killing of the form of author's neologism, the author notes the following: the discrepancy of the inner form of ordinary words and phraseologists in compared languages, which leads to the mismatch of signs and images that are laid on the basis of the Occasionalism lexical units; the difference between the wording systems and norms of use of words; Requirements of the transition context. Thus, when translating the Occasionalism, it is important to pay attention to the external form of words and the degree of its deviation from the rate of the PA, since this will affect the degree of occasionalism of the cospecting of the coscodealism. Also, it should always be taken into account the context, since it helps to catch the full lexical value of the Okacelism and, therefore, correctly transfer it to the PA.

Speaking about the lexical value of the occasionalism, it is important to remember that it is multicomponent and is obtained with the help of semantic compression. More B. Shcherb believed that "the rules for the addition of meanings, which do not give the sum of the meanings, and the new meanings are extremely important, but not yet to the end are

investigated. The concept of compression in linguistics is interpreted in different ways. It is understood as in a broad sense as a common trend in the language to simplification and compression, and in a more narrowest sense of like

1) "omission of words duplicating the part of the meaning of another word of the same sentence" ;

2) "Compressing the planning meaning (words) when maintaining the plan for the meaningful (concept).

Compression occurs at different levels of language. For example, the first definition implies a syntactic compression. In this paper, we are interested in the semantic compression that occurs within one word. Under it, we will understand the process of condensation of components - the seven, whose goal is to transfer the maximum amount of information to the minimum number of language. To identify the final value of the occasionalism, a component analysis is used. By conducting a component analysis, we can judge the type of relationship established between the occasionalism and its canonical synonym. One of the options for such a communication of occasionalism and the canonical word is the relationship of the private opposition . Print opposition - Enabling the value of one word (B) to the value of the other (A) (b). This proves that the occasionalism has an extended and complicated value. P. Newmark believes that component analysis in linguistics is significantly different from the component analysis used in transmission. If in the first case we are limited to the fact that we are outstanding the lexical unit to the SEMES (then Software, in the second case - this is the process of comparing the original word and its translation and the detection of similar and various: Thus, the component analysis is an important stage in the translation of the occasionalism of the Land, as it helps to reveal their complicated value and its additional shades that should also be transferred to the PA, and choose the most suitable translation option that would fully correspond to the seal of the original word.

References:

1. Yoriyeva Zarifa Hamroyevna , OKKAZIONALIZMLARNING BADIY ASAR TAHLILI VA TARAQQIYOTIDAGIO'RNI 10.5281/zenodo.6567693.
2. Toshaliyeva S. O'zbek tilida okkazionalizmlar. Nomzodlik dissertatsiyasi. — T.: 1998.
3. Половина, Л. В. (2023). Оксюмороны в речи и художественной литературе. In *СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ* (pp. 116-118).
4. Polovina, L. V. (2022). Features of the Study of Subordinate Tense in Schools with the Uzbek Language of Instruction. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 109-114.
5. Gulomovna, K. Z., & Inomovna, I. H. (2019). Project Method in Teaching English. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 7.
6. Saydaliyevna, Saliyeva Shaxlo, and Abdulkhamidov Sanjarbek Husniddin o'g'li. "PECULIARITIES OF TRANSLATION OF SCIENTIFIC DEGREES." *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* 3.2 (2023): 102-107.
7. Shakhlo, Saliyeva. "Difficulties in language learning and types of errors." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN:

2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.09 (2022): 296-299.

8. Shakhlo, Saliyeva. "INTERACTIVE METHODS AND ACTIVITIES IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.12 (2022): 418-421.

9. Saydaliyevna, Saliyeva Shaxloxon. "The Description of Vocabulary, and the Role of its Acquisition in Teaching Foreign Language." European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science 6 (2022): 180-182.

10. Ergashevna, Ernazarova Khilola. "FORMING THE RIGHT PRONUNCIATION IN LANGUAGE TEACHING FORMATION OF SKILLS." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.09 (2022): 304-307.

11. Khamidova, Nargiza. "THE ORIGIN OF THE CATEGORY OF INTENSITY IN LINGUISTICS AND STAGES OF ITS DEVELOPMENT." ПРИКЛАДНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОДИНАМИКА, ФОТОНИКА И ЖИВЫЕ СИСТЕМЫ. VIII Молодежная международная научно-техническая конференция молодых ученых, аспирантов и студентов. Казань. Kazan National Research Technical University named after AN Tupolev, 2021.

12. Ergashevna, Ernazarova Hilola. "LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PROVERBS AND TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH PROVERBS." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.12 (2022): 426-428.

13. Ergashevna, Ernazarova Hilola. "Some peculiarities of entries and introductory sentences in a short text." ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 12.6 (2022): 253-256.

14. ҚЎЗИБОЕВА, О., & ХАМИДОВА, Н. ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИНИ ТАБИЙ ГЕОГРАФИК ЖИХАТДАН РАЙОНЛАШТИРИШИ. Бахтинур АБДУЖАББОРОВ.

15. Ismoilova, K. (2022). INFLUENCE OF WORDS FROM THE FIELD OF "IT" ON THE UZBEK LANGUAGE AND ITS LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS. ICARHSE. ICARHSE International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities France, Conference <https://confrencea.org> November 15th 2022

16. Ismoilova, K. (2022). The Submission of Uzbek Diplomatic Terms in the Dictionaries. European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science <https://emjms.academicjournal.io/index.php/> Volume: 7

17. QIZI, H. N. N. (2022). THE CATEGORY OF INSENSITIVITY IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR SPECIFIC FEATURES IN ENGLISH, RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 374-377.

18. Ismoilova, K. (2022). THE THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF METAPHOR IN A COGNITIVE ASPECT. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education.(INT-JECS) ISSN: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 04 2022

19. Khamidova, N. N. "Features of phraseological units in linguoculture. Современные проблемы филологии, педагогики и методики преподавания языков." Сборник научных трудов по итогам всероссийской научно-практической конференции. Kazan. 2020.

20. Raskhodova I. A., Khamidova N. N. HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS //ПРИКЛАДНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОДИНАМИКА, ФОТОНИКА И ЖИВЫЕ СИСТЕМЫ-2021. – 2021. – С. 552-554.

